

SUPPLEMENTS

FOR

Variation in personality shaped by evolutionary history, genotype, and developmental plasticity in response to feeding modalities in the Arctic charr

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Figure S1 – The five Arctic charr morphs studied (species: *Salvelinus alpinus*). Note the important differences in coloration, body depth, head and mouth morphology and in size (see scales in cm). **(A)** Large Benthic (LB) and **(B)** Planktivorous (PL) sympatric morphs from Þingvallavatn: top rows – photograph of each morph in left lateral view (Modified from: Sandlund OT, Gunnarsson K, Jónasson PM, Jonsson B, Magnússon KP, Malmquist HJ, et al. The arctic charr *Salvelinus alpinus* in Thingvallavatn. *Oikos*. 1992;64(1/2):305–51. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3545056>); Second, third and fourth rows – drawings of the head and feeding apparatus for each morph in dorsal, left lateral and ventral views respectively, illustrating the typical differences in feeding apparatus morphology respectively between benthic (A) vs. pelagic (B) morphs (Modified from: Snorrason SS, Skúlason S, Jonsson B, Malmquist HJ, Jónasson PM, Sandlund OT, et al. Trophic specialization in Arctic charr *Salvelinus alpinus* (Pisces; Salmonidae): morphological divergence and ontogenetic niche shifts. *Biological Journal of the Linnean Society*. 1994;52(1):1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-8312.1994.tb00975.x>). **(C)** Photograph of the Silver (VS, top row) and the Brown (VB, bottom row) sympatric morphs from Vatnshlíðarvatn in left lateral view (Photograph courtesy: Skúli Skúlason). **(D)** Photograph of the anadromous morph (AN) from Fjllótaá River in left lateral view (Photograph courtesy: Samantha V. Beck).

Figure S2 – Principal Component Analysis (PCA) on the first OFT replication, used to obtain individual boldness scores (see Chapter I of the R script accompanying the main text: *Dellinger M, Steele SE, Sprockel E, Philip J, Pálsson A, Benhaïm D. Variation in personality shaped by evolutionary history, genotype, and developmental plasticity in response to feeding modalities in the Arctic charr. Dryad Repository. 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.4f4qrfjk2>*). Shelter.duration, Entry.duration and Center.duration (s): cumulative time spent respectively in the shelter, entry and centre zones; Dtot (cm): total distance travelled; Entry.freq: frequency of visits in the entry zone; v.ang (deg.s⁻¹): absolute angular velocity. **(A)** PCA Factor map on PC1 and PC2 **(B)** Contributions and correlations per variable, eigenvalue, variance proportion and cumulative variance, for each PC dimension. **Comment:** non-responding fish (N = 73 out of 540 fish tested, see Table 2 in the main text and Table S1 for details) were not included in the PCA analyses because attributing them all with the same arbitrary boldness score, hence considering them all equally shy, is nonsensical in the context of testing for among-individual differences in behaviour. Indeed, if the test could last an infinite amount of time, each individual would eventually exit the shelter, behave differently in the arena, and consequently have their own boldness score. A single boldness score attributed to all non-responding fish would just fallaciously skew and bias the overall boldness score distribution, potentially in a tremendous way depending on the score arbitrarily chosen, and create a ceiling effect. Instead, proportions of non-responding fish were compared between groups using χ^2 tests (see results in the main text and in Table 2).

Figure S3 - Boxplots of boldness scores across the three families within each morph, from the least to the most diverged morph: AN from Fjlótaá River, sympatric VS and VB from Vatnshlíðarvatn, and sympatric LB and PL from Þingvallavatn. The rhombus represents the mean, grey dots are scattered individual values, the central line indicates the median, ends of the boxes denote upper and lower quartiles, whiskers cover 95% of values. Note that variation in boldness scores between families within a morph were similar, with just one oddity in PL, where family PL.1 displayed more variability than PL.2 and PL.3.

Table S1 – Sample size distribution between treatments, tank replicates and families for each morph, indicating the number of fish included in the analyses. Each replicate tank contained a total density of 136 fish, but only experimental fish are listed here. Fish from AN and LB morphs were distributed over three replicate tanks per treatment and per morph. VB crossings only provided enough individuals to be distributed over two replicate tanks per treatment. Variation in the experimental design/distribution concerning VS and PL morphs was due to the rearing of additional families not included in this study (that is, VS and PL families not represented in all replicate tanks, and discrepancies in the number of replicate tanks in PL). Families were however equally distributed over each replicate tank. For each family, 18 individuals were tested per treatment and per morph (6 or 9 fish per tank depending on the families' distribution and number of tank replicates). Discrepancies between theoretical and actual sample size for each subgroup are either due to individuals excluded from analyses for not responding to the OFT, or other reasons detailed in the footnote.

Morph	Family	Treatment Benthic			Treatment Pelagic		
		Replicate 1	Replicate 2	Replicate 3	Replicate 1	Replicate 2	Replicate 3
AN	AN.1	6	6	4	3	5	4
	AN.2	6	6	6	4	6	5
	AN.3	3	5	5	4	5	4
VS	VS.1	9	9			7	8
	VS.2		7	9	8	6	
	VS.3	7		8	8		8
VB	VB.1	8	7 ⁻¹		8	8	
	VB.2	6	6 ⁻¹		6 ⁺¹	9	
	VB.3	7	8		5	8	
LB	LB.1	6	9 ⁺³	6	5	6	5
	LB.2	3 ⁻¹	4	3 ⁻²	5	3	2 ⁻¹
	LB.3	5	7 ⁺¹	6	3 ⁻²	6	6
PL	PL.1	9		9	9	9	
	PL.2		9		9	9	
	PL.3	9		9	8 ⁻¹	9	

Superscript figures: the number of fish that died before the second OFT replication and hence not included in the analyses (negative superscript, nine fish in total), or supernumerary fish due to technical mismatch included in the analyses (positive superscript, five fish in total). Eventually, 463 out of 540 fish were included in the analyses, with 73 fish being excluded for not responding to the OFT test.

Table S2 – Estimates per treatment (B: Benthic and P: Pelagic) within morphs (AN from Fjlótaá River, sympatric VS and VB from Vatnshlíðarvatn, and sympatric LB and PL from Þingvallavatn), pairwise differences in the posterior distributions between treatments within morphs (Δ) and their effect sizes, of among-individual variance, within-individual variance and repeatability of boldness (*Vamong*, *Vwithin* and R respectively). Results were obtained from morph-specific multi-level structure Bayesian brms linear mixed models for boldness score, including the treatment as fixed predictor, random effects for both the intercept and the treatment-related effect nested within the individual IDs, and a sigma term accounting for potential variations in the residual standard deviation among treatments. See “Supplemental Chapter” in the R script accompanying the main text (Dellinger M, Steele SE, Sprockel E, Philip J, Pálsson A, Benhaïm D. *Variation in personality shaped by evolutionary history, genotype, and developmental plasticity in response to feeding modalities in the Arctic charr*. *Dryad Repository*. 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.4f4qrjfk2>). Significant Δ estimates and large effect sizes are highlighted in bold black font, while tendencies for Δ and small effect sizes are highlighted in bold grey font. **Estimates & Δ** : all estimates are medians of posterior distributions with their 95% credible interval (CI), along with probability of direction (PD) of the Δ , indicating the proportion of samples that are of the estimate’s sign, *i.e.*, roughly the probability that the estimate is different from zero. **Effect size**: probability of superiority (A) with its standard error (SE) and 95% confidence interval (CI), between the posterior distributions of each variable for each pair of morphs. The A statistic is a probability-based measure of effect size, indicating the probability that a randomly chosen member of group 1 scores higher on the response variable than a randomly chosen member of group 2, *i.e.*, in our case if $A < 0.5$, benthic fish outscore pelagic fish and *vice versa*. **Commentary**: We did not have sufficient power for these tests to show significant results except for very large differences, and a higher sample size and/or more numerous OFT replications would most likely turn these tendencies to significance, as suggested in Dingemans NJ, Dochtermann NA. *Quantifying individual variation in behaviour: Mixed-effect modelling approaches*. *Journal of Animal Ecology*. 2013;82(1):39–54. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2656.12013> and in Royauté R, Dochtermann NA. *Comparing ecological and evolutionary variability within datasets*. *Behavioral Ecology and Sociobiology*. 2021;75:127. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00265-021-03068-3>. But the results still show an interesting pattern: the morphs seemed to respond differently to the treatments in terms of boldness consistency (lower repeatability in the pelagic treatment for the sympatric morphs from Vatnshlíðarvatn, the contrary for the PL from Þingvallavatn, and no difference for its sympatric counterpart LB and the AN) suggesting that the environment in interaction with the genotype could be an important driver for the emergence and development of consistent behaviours among-individuals, *i.e.*, personality. It is worth noting that boldness repeatability seems higher when the treatment mimics the proper ecology of the morph: higher in the benthic treatment for morphs feeding close to the bottom in shallow environments like the VS and VB; equal between treatments for the benthic-feeder LB that however lives in a deep lake in which pelagic lifestyle is accessible, and the AN morph switching between shallow rivers and deeper seas; higher in the pelagic treatment for the PL feeding in deep open waters. This would suggest that the expression of behavioural consistency could be favoured when the environment meets the conditions for which the genotype has been adapted to, whereas the lack of behavioural consistency would highlight a situation of maladaptiveness. Notably, the potential behavioural maladaptiveness to benthic conditions expressed during juvenile stage in the PL could be hypothesized to be the origin of the ontogenetic shift from benthic spawning grounds to the pelagos in this morph (personality profiles engendering differential niche picking). However, this statement should be taken with caution, as our fully lab-based design focuses on only one aspect of foraging, still far from mimicking all the potential selective and developmental cues available in nature, and as expression of boldness in the lab might not necessarily fully reflect natural behaviours. Further research is hence needed to confirm or infirm the hypothesis that personality emerges as a result of an interaction between genes and environment in the Arctic charr, potentially in an adaptive way.

Variable	Morph	Estimates				Δ (P - B)				Effect size			
		Treatment	Estimate	Lower CI	Upper CI	Estimate	Lower CI	Upper CI	PD	A	SE	Lower CI	Upper CI
R	AN	B	0.11	0.00	0.39	-0.07	-0.36	0.13	0.75	0.25	0.01	0.24	0.26
		P	0.02	0.00	0.21								
	VS	B	0.30	0.03	0.55	-0.19	-0.48	0.18	0.85	0.15	0.00	0.14	0.16
		P	0.09	0.00	0.38								
	VB	B	0.32	0.01	0.57	-0.16	-0.49	0.22	0.78	0.22	0.01	0.21	0.23
		P	0.14	0.00	0.42								
	LB	B	0.24	0.01	0.49	0.08	-0.31	0.43	0.64	0.64	0.01	0.63	0.66
		P	0.32	0.03	0.56								
	PL	B	0.16	0.00	0.41	0.39	0.07	0.66	0.99	0.99	0.00	0.99	0.99
		P	0.56	0.35	0.72								
Vamong	AN	B	0.09	0.00	0.37	-0.05	-0.33	0.19	0.70	0.31	0.01	0.29	0.32
		P	0.03	0.00	0.26								
	VS	B	0.82	0.08	1.87	-0.57	-1.67	0.42	0.87	0.12	0.00	0.12	0.13
		P	0.20	0.00	0.96								
	VB	B	1.05	0.05	2.41	-0.55	-2.15	0.84	0.78	0.22	0.01	0.21	0.23
		P	0.44	0.00	1.56								
	LB	B	0.66	0.02	1.60	0.17	-1.01	1.47	0.61	0.61	0.01	0.60	0.62
		P	0.82	0.07	1.92								
	PL	B	0.14	0.00	0.44	0.71	0.22	1.36	1.00	1.00	0.00	1.00	1.00
		P	0.86	0.46	1.48								
Vwithin	AN	B	0.72	0.49	1.02	0.37	-0.04	0.84	0.96	0.96	0.00	0.96	0.96
		P	1.09	0.80	1.51								
	VS	B	1.89	1.27	2.89	0.05	-1.09	1.12	0.54	0.54	0.01	0.53	0.56
		P	1.95	1.35	2.79								
	VB	B	2.29	1.49	3.68	0.39	-1.15	1.84	0.69	0.70	0.01	0.69	0.71
		P	2.71	1.83	3.93								
	LB	B	2.09	1.41	3.15	-0.28	-1.49	1.01	0.67	0.31	0.01	0.30	0.33
		P	1.80	1.21	2.88								
	PL	B	0.77	0.54	1.09	-0.08	-0.48	0.31	0.67	0.33	0.01	0.32	0.34
		P	0.68	0.47	1.01								